

DEVELOPMENT OF STRATEGIC AND FUNCTIONAL MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

Tilaev Ermat Rahmatovich

Shahrisabz State Pedagogical Institute Dean of the Faculty of Social Sciences, Candidate of technical sciences

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Abstract. *This article will explore the significance of management in higher educational system and its theoretical foundations will be provided.*

Keywords: *general principle, hierarchy, innovation, operational management.*

In the conditions of rapid development of scientific and technical processes, the implementation of innovative activities places special demands on the management system in the context of the reforms being carried out in our country. Functional management - special attention is paid to management activities aimed at forming and achieving the goals of innovative development of the organization through the effective use of material, labor and financial resources. Functional management in a higher education institution is a collection of scientifically based principles, methods, methods and means of mastering in the educational process in order to manage them in the field of creating innovations, increase the quality of education and promote them in the market for profit. The main goal of functional management is to ensure the long-term operation and development of the educational institution based on the effective organization of innovative processes and the high level of competitiveness of the innovative product, the maximization of the effectiveness of commercialization of the innovation. Strategic innovation management: development of a strategy of priorities for the development of a higher educational institution, expansion to the market of educational services, analysis of the external environment and the market of educational services, strategic decisions on the development of the educational institution and its mission, its dynamic development and competitiveness, the fulfillment of the mission of the educational institution and its development implies.

Functional innovation management concentrates its functions in the specific activities of innovation development, introduction, production and commercialization management. Operational management focuses on the short and medium term perspective. Operational management systems have sufficiently complete information, are characterized by a low level of uncertainty and are directed to the lower and middle levels of management.

The decisive factor for the effective introduction of innovations is the composition of professors and teachers of a higher education institution and its attitude to employees. Therefore, the task of leaders in the introduction of innovations is to form the psychological readiness of pedagogues, which is manifested in the realization of the timely implementation of the innovation, the personal and collective importance of the innovation, as well as the need to personally engage in the implementation of the innovation.

The laws of educational management reflect the objectively existing and repeated serious interrelationships of various elements and events in the management process. Their general and

specific are different. General laws are characteristic of all management systems, and private laws are related to the activities of individual educational institutions and organizations.

General principles of educational management it is characterized by the fact that it has a universal character and affects all areas of management.

The general principles of management consist of: goal orientation, planning, competence, discipline, motivation, hierarchy.

Principle of goal orientation. It is determined by the programmatic nature of management and implies setting clear goals for each educational management body and each of its divisions. In this case, the goal should be realistic, achievable and absolutely clearly defined, which gives a healthy meaning to the work and mobilizes the efforts of employees to fulfill it. The principle of planning. Establishing a program of actions defined by program-targeted management and intended to carry it out. It is manifested in the regulation of working conditions and its distribution among the performers, coordination of the actions of the performers and their instruction, as well as control and reporting on the execution of each job and the entire program. The principle of competence. It is related to the horizontal division of labor according to the task. Knowledge of the object of management by the manager or, at least, his ability to perceive the competent advice of experts in decision-making.

The principle of discipline. It should be present in any management system at any level. The role of this principle is especially great when it comes to education, because the specificity of the field determines not only executive discipline, but also financial discipline and increased requirements for self-discipline of each employee, from the minister to the pedagogue. At the same time, discipline should not stifle the initiative of employees and leave room for creative attitude to work.

The incentive principle. First of all, it means motivating labor activity based on material and moral incentives. Financial incentives are based on the personal economic benefit of employees from the results of their work, and moral incentives are mainly based on the psychological impact on employees. Promotion also includes moral incentives and motivations, fair treatment of employees.

The principle of hierarchy. It envisages the vertical division of management work, that is, the separation of management levels and the subordination of lower levels to higher ones. It is taken into account in the formation of the organizational structure of the management, the construction of the management apparatus, and the placement of personnel. All principles of management are interrelated and define each other. For example, the precise functioning of the management system cannot be achieved without denying its other principles (goal orientation, planning, competence, motivation, hierarchy). Similarly, goal-oriented activities cannot be organized without planning, competence, discipline and hierarchy.

The role of integrating strategic and functional management, specific principles and components of management are described. Today, the system of training and retraining of management personnel is constantly being improved, and the implemented innovations are largely related to the introduction of various innovations into the educational process. In modern scientific literature, there are more and more references to the description of various objects, events and processes, which are considered as a consequence of the introduction of innovations. Naturally, the emergence of new scientific and professional directions requires a specialized system of

training managers, in which not only the content of management, but also its methods and tools should correspond to the appropriate stage of the development of a higher education institution.

It is necessary to emphasize that in order to effectively develop management competencies, leaders need to look for new methods and principles that help a person-oriented approach, flexibility in solving problems, and a non-standard approach to management.

Thus, the analysis of the peculiarities of professional management activities of pedagogical personnel in terms of integration of strategic and functional management made it possible to distinguish the following components of innovative management: motivational, informative, communicative and innovative.

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Learning management functions - types of activities with the help of which the management subsystem affects the management object. Management functions are also divided into general and private (special) functions. Common functions are common to all control systems. And private functions have certain peculiarities.

In relation to management, the following general functions are distinguished: strategic planning, organization, motivation, control.

Methods of educational management - methods of the subject of management to influence the managed object to achieve certain goals. Educational management methods are diverse, but their impact on employees (the staff of the educational institution in general and each employee individually) is mediated by motivation.

Needs and interests play an important role in human behavior.

A need is a physiological and psychological feeling of a lack of something by a person. Rewards are everything that a person considers valuable for himself. Human activity determines the economic, external-command and social-psychological directions of total management methods of the needs aimed at achieving them.

In order to achieve maximum efficiency in management, moral motivations are needed, which direct socio-psychological methods of management. With the help of these methods, employees' consciousness, social, moral and other interests of people are influenced and moral stimulation of labor activity is carried out. Spiritual motivation is characterized by special complexity and subtlety. It is very difficult to determine its final effect, but its results are quite significant. Management methods usually have a complex effect on all of the listed types of motives, so it is not correct to divide them into primary and secondary methods, and put them against each other. On the contrary, they should be viewed in unity and interrelation, because their complex application helps to achieve the set goals at the optimal level. The increasingly common methods of optimizing management decisions are mathematical modeling, expert evaluation, "brainstorming", game theory, etc. is considered

A control function is a relationship between a control system and a controlled object that requires the control system to perform certain action(s) to ensure that the controlled processes are

goal-directed or coordinated. Management actions differ in their content and results. This is also the reason for the differentiation of management functions.

In addition to the characteristics of the managed object, the composition of functions is also influenced by the approach to management. Looking at the evolution of management thought, we observed that different approaches have different understandings of "what" and "how" should be done in the management process in order for it to be effective. In the rationalist approach focused on the "whip and dessert" method, the informal structure of the organization is outside the field of attention of managers, and management functions are not performed in relation to it. In individual-oriented approaches, on the contrary, the satisfaction of the members of the organization, the socio-psychological environment in the team, the values that apply in it become the subject of analysis and management.

However, as noted above, there is no single best approach to management. One approach may be more effective in some circumstances, and the other in others. This means that the composition of the implemented management functions should also be adequate to the situation.

The composition of these functions also largely depends on the direction of development of the higher education institution. If the task that the administration of a higher education institution tries to solve is to support the stable operation of a higher education institution, the functions of managing innovative processes are not implemented at all, or are implemented to a very small extent. On the contrary, in an innovative higher education institution, the time spent on managing the processes of searching and assimilating innovations will be proportional to the time spent on the functions of managing the educational process.

Therefore, we understand the management process as a continuous sequence of actions, which are carried out by the subject of management and as a result of which the image and content of the managed object are formed and changed, the goals of cooperative activity are determined, the methods of achieving them, the work is distributed among its participants and their efforts are integrated .

The principles of innovation management are scientifically based basic goals that determine the goals, forms and methods of implementing innovative activity of organizations. These are the principles of decision-making based on the added facts, the principle of looking for unrealized opportunities, etc.

Innovation management performs certain functions that determine the formation of the management system of the higher education institution during the implementation of the innovation process. Two groups of innovation management: basic and supporting functions are distinguished.

Accordingly, the mechanisms of integration of strategic and functional management in an educational institution can be realized in stages as follows:

Stage I - the realization of the importance, necessity and inevitability of future changes by one of the members of the administrative team of the educational institution, that is, the presence of a specific "ideal inspiration" and "generator" of future ideas.

Stage II – in our case, not only the administrative (managerial) team, but also the formation of a team of ideological supporters, who are methodically and technologically ready to introduce this or that innovation, among the members of the pedagogical team.

Stage III - selection of the innovation development and implementation strategy. Motivating the members of the pedagogical team and forming the readiness of pedagogues for innovative activities.

Stage IV - forecasting and problem analysis of the future of the educational institution, building a "problem area" and defining the main problem in one's institution.

Stage V - search, selection and development of a project idea for the development of the educational institution in the nearest period based on the results of the problem analysis and the identified main problem.

Stage VI – determination of specific management actions based on the developed idea, i.e. a) determination of the goal of innovation management, b) selection of innovation management strategy, c) creation of a plan or program for its implementation, g) determination of innovation management methods.

Stage VII – monitoring of the steps to implement the project idea in order to correct further management actions.

Stage VIII - control of the implementation of the specified program. Analysis and evaluation of innovation management methods. Correction of innovation management methods.

By strategic management activity integrated with functional management, we understand the activity of systematic objects and subjects of education, their dynamics and direct educational process. Regulatory management activities are based on the comparison of the results of pedagogical influence with the existing normative and criteria. In addition, planning results can be used to forecast the dynamics of pedagogical processes, as well as to evaluate pedagogical phenomena.

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